

NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS IN TEACHING MUSIC CULTURE IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS.

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Abstract.

This article deals with the design of pedagogical technologies for the lessons of music culture and the effective organization of the lesson.

Keywords.

Pedagogical technology, project, technical means, interactive methods, technological training.

Annotasiya.

Ushbu maqolamizda musiqa madaniyati darslariga pedagogik texnologiyalarni loyixalashtirish va darsni samarali tashkil etish bo'yicha so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar.

Pedagogik texnologiya, loyixa, texnik vositalar, interfaol usullar, texnologik trening.

Аннотация.

В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы проектирования педагогических технологий на уроках музыкальной культуры и эффективной организации урока.

Ключевые слова.

Педагогическая технология, проект, технические средства, интерактивные методы, технологический тренинг.

At the stage of new development of Uzbekistan, the changes and renewals taking place in our country are being implemented on the basis of strong spiritual and moral values. This shows that the place and role of education is important in the formation of high qualities of young people and, at the same time, in expanding their spiritual outlook. There are a number of principles of new pedagogical technology in the course of music lessons in secondary schools, such as organizing an interesting lesson based on the general purpose of the lesson, testing the student's knowledge based on test questions, designing problems in the form of questions and answers based on situations, and consists of others. Mixing such methods, not straining the child, using methods taking into account his age is a

characteristic that a teacher-pedagogue should know. A music teacher should increase students' interest in the lesson and use new pedagogical technologies effectively and appropriately, as well as organize the lesson with the help of appropriate forms, methods and tools. Including: technical tools, computer and other musical instrument styles, demonstration equipment, practical exercises, pedagogical and psychological tools are the advanced experience and skills of an advanced teacher. The idea of technology of education is not new. 400 years ago, the Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius put forward the idea of technological education.

He encouraged education to be "technical", that is, everything should be taught to be successful. He called the educational process leading to the result "didactic machine". Specific goals for such a didactic machine; to achieve these goals, clearly adapted means; wrote that it is important to find clear rules for how to use these tools. In the theory and practice of education, the first attempts were made in the 1950s to give the educational process a technological character. They express themselves in the creation of complex technical tools designed for traditional teaching. Currently, "pedagogical technology" is not considered as technical means of education or research in the field of computer use, but through the analysis of factors that increase educational efficiency, the creation and application of methods and materials, as well as the methods used. is that it clearly aims to determine the principles of the educational process and develop the most optimal ways through assessment. It is known from the development of the countries of the world that the economic development of any country depends on the moral level of the people living in it.

However, the socio-economic and spiritual development of independent Uzbekistan at the level of developed countries in the world is in many ways oriented towards the development of the young generation, which can freely enter into new social relations, recognizes universal human values, and is oriented towards spiritual values. depends on the development of active, highly cultured, qualified personnel. In particular, examples of culture, value, and national art are widely used in the education of young people. In the educational system, great importance is attached to the issue of using the tradition of "Teacher - student". At all levels of the education system, "Education of our children as truly patriotic people with independent thinking, modern knowledge and professional skills, and a strong life position is a matter of urgent importance for us" 1, our president Sh. Mirziyoyev [1,489 p]. Therefore, the application of innovative, i.e., advanced pedagogical technologies to the educational system in the spiritual education of

students in music lessons is the demand of the time. Research on new pedagogical technologies belongs to scientists such as V.P. Bepalko, N.Shodiyev, M.Ochilov, N.Azizkhojayeva, O'.Tolipov, but music-related technologies are not widely covered in their scientific works. With this in mind, we think about the possibilities of designing and planning pedagogical technologies for the process of music culture lessons and improving the quality of music education using these technologies. The purpose of our article is to introduce pedagogical ways of using new pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of musical education. It is aimed at studying the theoretical foundations of the formation of the use of pedagogical technologies in young people through musical training, and then their practical ways.

Therefore, if we consider the use of pedagogical technologies that must be designed in music culture classes of general education schools: 1. Studying the essence of the use of new pedagogical technologies in music culture classes, educating students' musical thinking. exit; 2. To determine the possibilities of using pedagogical technologies to educate students spiritually in music culture classes; 3. Determining the content, form, methods and means of using pedagogical technologies in the process of educating their growing students in musical qualities, determining their effectiveness and making recommendations; If the work is carried out on the basis of this project, it is explained by the fact that the methods of educating students in musical education qualities and using pedagogical technologies have been developed in the course of music culture lessons. In the process of music culture classes, the mechanisms of applying modern new pedagogical technologies and projecting them into the educational process are revealed. In this regard, the well-known scientist of music pedagogy, Dildora Karimova, conducted scientific research on the problem of "Basics of musical pedagogical skills", and it was fully analyzed in the process of music lessons in secondary schools of our Republic. The main issue is the musical-emotional perception and emotional perception of each student. The content, forms and methods of using new pedagogical technologies in the spiritual education of students were also developed in the music culture lessons of the general education school, the "Music Science" textbooks. It can be observed that new methods and tools are being rapidly implemented in pedagogical practice. However, instead of some educational forms and active methods, indivisible educational technologies are necessary.

However, technological design and planning of the educational process can only be done by a teacher who has technological knowledge, skills and

qualifications. Because, in music culture classes, the process of spiritual education of students through new pedagogical technologies is carried out through class activities. They found their expression in the creation of complex technical tools for traditional and non-traditional teaching. Currently, pedagogical technology is not considered as research in the field of technical means of teaching or the use of computers. is aimed at determining the basis of the process and the development of ways to optimize it. Transferring all educational and educational work to the path of pedagogical technology means a sharp departure from the voluntary construction and implementation of the pedagogical process of school practice. That is why we teachers should design advanced pedagogical technologies in the lesson process and apply it widely. In the course of the lesson, it is appropriate to provide students with pedagogical technology and education together. It is necessary for the teacher to form the spiritual, artistic, and moral culture of the students, to ensure that they will realize the education of national pride and patriotism. As it is known, "Pedagogy" as a science of education means to understand the essence of education and reveal its laws, and thereby human interests affect the process of education. This will definitely help in solving many problems. In addition to the experience of advanced pedagogical trainers, the activities of ordinary teachers are also studied.

The musical culture of general education schools should treat students as individuals during the lesson, use various pedagogical technologies and modern methods to encourage them to think independently, freely, to search, to approach each issue creatively, and to feel responsibility. conduct scientific research, analysis, effective use of scientific literature, and most importantly, strengthen interests in study, science, pedagogy, and the chosen profession. In general, instead of a conclusion, it should be noted that achieving such a result in practice requires the use of design and pedagogical technologies in the educational process. They are very different. These include new interactive methods and educational methods, as well as new pedagogical technologies currently used in the classroom. It should be noted that if the above-mentioned modern pedagogical technologies and technological trainings that help to increase the effectiveness of planning and teaching are widely used, mental, creative and independent thinking will be formed in students. It will greatly help them to develop their abilities, to become mature specialists and to increase the professional qualities necessary for a specialist.

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